

Modular Real-Time Monitoring System Architecture for Materials and Technologies to Improve Urban Heat-Island Effect and Water Runoff in HE MULTICLIMACT

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Abstract—Given the threat of climate change and the associated growth in extreme events, it is imperative to improve the planning, design, and upgrading of the built environment at different scales to effectively adapt to current and future risks. Therefore, the MULTICLIMACT project (MULTI-faceted CLIMATE adaptation ACTIONS to improve resilience, preparedness, and responsiveness of the built environment against multiple hazards at multiple scales) seeks to provide an integrated framework of tools to assist public actors and citizens at territorial, urban and individual building levels. At all these scales, real-time monitoring and early warning systems are seen as key tools to improve preparedness and responsiveness. At the urban level, the scale of this paper, it is considered a key issue that the built environment is nowadays often itself a source of climate vulnerability rather than a safe place for its inhabitants. Based on these two key points, this contribution focuses on the design of a modular real-time monitoring system architecture, combining Internet of Things (IoT) sensor networks, signal processing, Artificial Intelligence (AI) data analysis and Building Information Modeling (BIM) visualization, along with selection or development of sensors for cost-effective monitoring of the specific solutions to be implemented in the urban scale within MULTICLIMACT, namely new optimized cool urban pavement and nature-based solutions (NBS) designs to mitigate the heat-island effect and surface runoff, both identified as major risks in Europe's hot Mediterranean cities with low seismic risk, such as Barcelona (BCN), the future pilot city for the deployment of these solutions.

Keywords—IoT sensors, Fiber Optics Sensors, Artificial Intelligence, Digital Twin, Sustainable Urban Materials and Solutions

I. INTRODUCTION

The objective of the work is to monitor through a purpose-designed and graphically contextualized modular system the physical solutions specifically developed to mitigate the heat-island effect, and surface runoff in the case of the NBS, in urban areas, as one of the goals of the MULTICLIMACT project. As indicated in [1], the search for solutions to the heat-island effect is at the forefront of scientific research and policy development, requiring sustainable ways, among which are, on the one hand, the use of new pavements and materials in the city and, on the other hand, the increase of urban green

infrastructure in its various forms and utilities, with bioswales, in particular, playing an important role in mitigating surface runoff [2, 3]. Due to their orientation as exposed surfaces and their enormous extension (they occupy 20-40% of the surface area) in cities, one of the most sought-after solutions are "cool pavements", either by influencing their surface reflectivity / thermal properties / porosity / permeability [4]. The materials and technologies we propose for urban environments, for which the monitoring system solution is developed, are in line with these approaches and are currently under design (the project has a duration of 42 months and is in its first year or planning and design phase). In this phase of the project, they can be summarized as follows:

A. Cool pavement solution and its real-time monitoring requirements

This solution is centered in the design and advancement of innovative asphalt pavements with recycled material, mainly glass aggregates to reduce the heat capacity of outdoor pavements and mitigate the urban heat-island effect. The pavement needs to comply with the specifications of BCN Municipality and will be based in their typical asphalt section for the local network, where only modifications will be made to the wearing course as it is the layer where most of the interventions in the city are performed and which could become a replicable solution in the future in large-scale renovations. The option of a porous pavement for BCN has been discarded because it would be useless for cooling in this climate (the porous mixtures are only effective in areas where the rain is frequent and of moderate intensity) and weaker than other options. Thus, the wearing course is currently being designed (by COMSA) and will be a dense Asphalt Concrete (AC) layer with a % of glass recycled aggregate in the sand portion, between the 15 and 25% (to be determined, together with the other % of the final mixture, based on future tests). To enhance the effect of the recycled glass aggregates on lowering the temperature of the mixture, light color aggregates will be considered to improve reflectivity. Additives could also be studied to lighten the asphalt, but they tend to quickly lose their effectiveness with intensive use in cities. COMSA will conduct different tests (mechanical and thermal) during this plan and design phase to close the formulation for the mix.

Fig. 1. Example of recycled glass aggregate fractions considered.

As part of a strategy of continuous evaluation of the performance of new pavements in future BCN evaluation areas compared to standard pavements in existing nearby areas, the physical quantities to be continuously measured are:

- The internal strain in the asphalt layer (this is a new mix, so it is necessary to evaluate its operational mechanical behavior and its long-term evolution).
- The internal temperature of the asphalt layer and the external or city ambient temperature at different distances from the road pavement, both for areas with the new solution installed and for comparable areas with standard pavement.

Consequently, the monitoring KPIs will be:

- The reduction of external ambient temperature achieved with respect to analogous areas with standard pavement.
- The reduction of internal heat accumulation of the new pavement with respect to the normal one.

B. NBS solution to mitigate the urban heat-island effect and water runoff and its real-time monitoring requirements

This solution is focused on the design and development of innovative and optimized bio-retention swales to reduce the heat-island effect and more efficiently manage stormwater in urban contexts. This product combines hydrologic, environmental, and urbanistic aspects to favor in-site runoff retention, accumulation, and treatment to return water to the water bodies, to infiltrate or to direct reuse. At the same time, it introduces vegetation in urban areas offering heat regulation services through shading and evapotranspiration (ET), while providing several ecosystem services. Considering the typical components or structure of a bioretention facility ([5] among others), two specific and optimized solutions have been designed (by NATURALEA), one shallower and cheaper than the other, and both with only Mediterranean native plant species, without the need for irrigation or drainage pipes, to improve the resilience of the city in the terms already referred to, being the system virtually self-sufficient.

Fig. 2. Initial two designs of bioretention swales (by NATURALEA) within MULTICLIMACT.

As indicated, it is necessary to develop and deploy a customized continuous monitoring system, as cost-effective, adaptable and scalable as possible, as well as minimally visible in the urban environment in question, which is the main contribution of this paper. For the bioswale, the identified variables to be continuously retrieved in real time are:

- The internal water level (measured inside a vertical perforated pipe duly installed in the bioswale and protected by a geotextile).
- The external or ambient temperature and humidity in the areas of the city with these NBS installed and in the nearby areas without them.

Therefore, the monitoring KPIs are:

- The improvement of the external ambient temperature and humidity with respect to analogous non-equipped areas.
- The permeability and infiltration rate of the bioswale (given by the measured water level changes during and after rainfall).

II. ARCHITECTURE OF THE MONITORING SYSTEM

The real-time monitoring system was designed with a modular architecture in mind to take advantage of flexibility in integrating different types of sensors and communication protocols. As such, the system employs a hybrid local/cloud architecture to optimize both cost and performance. It deploys local infrastructure for real-time data collection and preprocessing, while leveraging the scalability of cloud services for batch storage, machine learning and analytics.

The local network layer implements middleware functionality on localized servers to enable faster ingestion and filtering of real-time sensor data closer to the edge before transmission over the wide area network. On the other hand, computationally intensive functions, such as distributed analytics and simulations, are hosted at the network layer in

the cloud to take advantage of the scalable processing power it offers without the need for large capital investments.

The split between real-time processing on-site and historical analysis in the cloud ensures low-latency anomaly detection that can trigger alerts and actions more quickly. Long-term patterns that affect solution optimization are still identified through cloud analytics. By selectively leveraging resources at the edge and in the cloud, the hybrid architecture provides a balance of cost-effectiveness, real-time performance and scalability.

As the deployment of the solution increases in larger urban areas, local middleware nodes can be added to maintain real-time responsiveness in a distributed topology. In addition, the centralized cloud repository provides a global view of aggregated data across the city for localized learning. The hybrid model is designed to maintain optimal costs by appropriately splitting processing loads. The overarching architecture consists of the five key layers presented below.

A. Sensors and communications

The system is adaptable to different sensors and their corresponding communication protocols (both detailed in chapter III) through small code changes in the middleware layer.

B. MQ Telemetry Transport (MQTT) Broker

The MQTT message broker is based on the lightweight MQTT protocol, which works on top of Transmission Control Protocol/Internet Protocol (TCP/IP). It provides a common interface to route sensor data from diverse devices using publish-subscribe messaging. It queues and routes the sensor data to upstream platforms for storage and analysis. Using MQTT allows asynchronous communication without needing continuous links between sensors and the broker.

In the case of Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor arrays, the fiber optic interrogator to which they connect can be interfaced to an on-premises Long-Term Evolution (LTE) router over 5G. The router then streams this real-time FBG data simultaneously to the cloud network for storage as well as the Digital Twin (DT) application for visualization and anomaly detection. The same infrastructure can be leveraged by other MQTT-enabled sensors for a unified data pipeline.

C. On-Premises Network

This layer consists of a middleware platform hosted on-site to ingest real-time sensor data, perform signal processing and filtering, run edge analytics models, and route data to cloud or visualization layers. The middleware is implemented through Node-RED flows, which is a current trend in most open IoT implementations (such as [6], [7]), providing flexibility to interface diverse sensors through MQTT or Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) connectors.

D. Cloud Network

A cloud-based data lake stores the filtered sensor data received from the on-premises middleware for historical analysis using scalable cloud computing resources. Batch analytics and machine learning models can be executed over the sensor data. The cloud network layer is implemented using Delta Lake technology and MLflow.

Delta Lake is an open-source storage layer that features ACID (Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation, and Durability)

transactions and provides a reliable, scalable, and efficient way to store and manage large amounts of data in a variety of formats, including structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data. On the other hand, MLflow is an open-source platform for managing the entire machine learning lifecycle, from experimentation to deployment.

E. Digital Twin Application

The filtered and analyzed sensor data is visualized through dashboards and Digital Twin applications to contextualize the performance of the implemented solutions. Digital Twin integrates sensor data with 3D models to provide intuitive actionable insights.

This modular architecture allows the monitoring system to easily interface with new sensors, scale across solutions deployed across the city, and deliver sensor data lifecycle management spanning real-time anomaly detection to historical analysis for performance optimization.

Fig. 3. Components of the monitoring system architecture, adapted from the work [8], by the same main authors, to the new solutions to be monitored (image arranged vertically for better legibility).

III. SELECTED SENSORS

A. In-house IoT Sensors

The proposed in-house IoT devices comprise energy-autonomous IoT sensors with integrated communications to measure multiple contextual parameters outside the solutions, i.e., in the nearby urban environment, such as temperature, humidity and noise, and other structural safety-related intermediate variables such as acceleration and tilt. This prototype stands out for its use of an ESP32 processor (microcontroller units or MCUs from a company called Espressif), which allows programming complex local operations such as obtaining Fourier transforms, among

others. It features a high-performance main accelerometer (to obtain directly or indirectly inertial variables without the need for a reference, i.e. acceleration, velocity and tilt), integrates low-power IoT communication through Sigfox and Long Range (LoRa) protocols to maximize availability across different low-power wireless networks, and has ports for connecting different external sensors to the board (for measuring temperature, humidity, wind, etc.). Regarding energy autonomous capabilities it is powered directly by a solar panel (5V max) and uses an e-peas AEM10941 solar harvesting integrated circuit with a 250F Lithium-Ion Capacitor (LIC). It also includes an additional external 250F capacitor.

The prototype leverages Edge Impulse [9] to become a powerful machine learning inference platform through edge computing, making them ideal for projects that require AI models optimized to run locally on embedded devices, enabling intelligence to be added to a wide range of IoT and industrial applications. During the project, the potential use of locally processed AI will be studied as an alternative or complement to its implementation in the cloud.

The custom wireless sensors play an important role in monitoring various environmental parameters (those external to the solutions) relevant to the future BCN pilot case. In addition, the accelerometers and tilt sensors of these prototypes can be used to monitor possible structural movements of the construction solutions applied in the pilot area, like the new pavement and the bioretention swale. Any displacement or simply variations due to environmental stresses or other phenomena could be detected and characterized by analyzing the patterns of these data over time. In addition, the environmental microphone can be used to monitor acoustic noise in the urban environment. Excessive noise levels are often correlated with high levels of activity and traffic, which can contribute to the urban heat-island effect through increased heat generation, that is, by continuously monitoring noise levels at multiple locations using the microphones, hotspots of high acoustic activity can be identified and correlated with temperature data to better understand heat buildup patterns. These are complementary studies and indicators to be explored in the deployment phase.

Fig. 4. Detail of the In-house IoT device developed by TECNALIA, with the capacity to centralize, preprocess and send measurements of interest in urban environments as an autonomous node, to which external Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) sensors can be attached to the motherboard.

The wireless connectivity through Sigfox and LoRa allows these sensors to stream data continuously to the central cloud platform without the need for proximate gateways. This

could enable a scalable and flexible deployment across the cityscape of BCN.

The edge processing capabilities can allow advanced signal processing and feature extraction to be performed locally before transmitting compact representations of data. This reduces bandwidth requirements and can identify data anomalies at the edge for more intelligent triggering of alerts.

Furthermore, machine learning and AI capabilities through the integration of Edge Impulse allow training models opening a wide range of study possibilities, for example, acoustic models could detect signatures of activities that contribute to heat generation, patterns can be identified in the evolution data of the ambient temperature in the city with the internal pavement temperature, etc.

B. Custom (Pre-commercial) FBG Arrays

There is not yet a consolidated solution on the market for measuring the interior of road surfaces in operation, but there are several alternatives with their pros and cons [10]. FBG-based sensors are currently the best candidate for embedding in urban pavements, as this fiber optic technology presents important advantages for this purpose, such as light weight, small size, immunity to electromagnetic interference, robustness and durability, as well as the ability to perform semi-continuous measurements along the same channel or array [11], being also a cutting-edge technology but mature enough to be applied in an operational scenario. In this case, a customized array with FBG strain and temperature sensors specially designed to be embedded in AC layers has been requested from the manufacturer Hottinger Brüel & Kjaer (HBK) [12], which produces it still in pre-commercial testing phase. The array has a semi-rigid casing to improve protection against high temperatures and rolling loads, and to provide a semi-continuous measurement of the actual strain and internal temperature of the asphalt pavement in which it is embedded without generating physical distortions in it. TECNALIA has experimentally verified that both temperature and deformation measurements match the reality of a controlled laboratory test at a representative scale, so this sensor is suitable to be used embedded in the "cool pavement" of COMSA to be installed in the city of BCN (pilot case at urban scale within MULTICLIMACT) to measure data for evaluating the mitigation of the heat-island effect and to control the mechanical behavior of this new formulation altered with recycled glass aggregates in the mix.

Fig. 5. Experimental specimen and test facilities (in TECNALIA's laboratory), and theoretical strain distribution to check the sensor (supplied by HBK) proposed to evaluate the new pavement (to be developed and installed by COMSA) in BCN city to mitigate the urban heat-island effect.

Fig. 6. Experimental results obtained for strain tests, which are in agreement with theoretical hypotheses applicable to mixed structures.

Fig. 7. Internal temperature curve after artificial heating, being possible to follow the evolution in real time of the heat retention by the material (a generic asphaltic matrix, not the new mixture) after a cessation of heating.

The arrays were connected to a QuantumX MXFS interrogator of the same manufacturer (HBK), from which a transmission to the monitoring system was successfully implemented through a standard computer via MQTT protocol and 3G/4G network, being this fiber wired monitoring setup also prepared for future deployment in urban environment.

C. Commercial Sigfox Sensors

An ultrasonic level sensor for liquid or flat surface (WSSFC-ULC) was selected to support the NBS product, particularly to measure water level evolution in the bioretention swale. It operates using low-power, long-range Sigfox connectivity, making it well-suited for battery-operated remote deployments.

In the case of BCN, these ultrasonic level sensors can be perfectly used to monitor the hydraulic behavior of the bioretention swales that are being implemented as a natural solution for urban rainwater management and urban cooling. For this purpose, it is proposed to place a vertical perforated pipe covered with geotextile inside the bioretention facility (its design will be adapted for this purpose at a later stage), so that the ultrasonic pulses can measure the water level variations inside the pipe during and after rainfall, thus obtaining an infiltration rate.

By correlating the swale water level data with concurrent rainfall data, the overall stormwater absorption and regulation performance of the bioswales can be comprehensively evaluated and characterized. This empirical data can guide design optimizations and inform deployment strategies to maximize the urban cooling and flood prevention benefits of this NBS.

On the other hand, wireless connectivity allows centralized collection of level data from multiple installations throughout BCN without the need for costly wired infrastructure, while long battery life minimizes maintenance needs.

Three WSSFC-ULC sensor units were procured and tested in a laboratory environment and were successfully connected to the monitoring system architecture. Also, one of the units was installed under a bridge close to a river to test the measurement capabilities of the devices in a real-world environment prior to the deployment in the BCN pilot.

Fig. 8. Test environment for the WSSFC-ULC sensor.

IV. BIM CONTEXTUALIZATION FOR DIGITAL TWIN OF THE URBAN-SCALE SOLUTIONS

Since we are dealing with building assets, this work applies a Digital Twin concept away from the industrial domain. Following the DT framework defined in [13], this implementation will be able to encapsulate the following features: Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) + IoT + BIM + AI (to be defined once real data is collected in later MULTICLIMACT's testing and deployment phases) + Decision Support (DS) through contextualized alerts. Although TECNALIA has its own viewer for BIM contextualization, the designed architecture of the customized monitoring system allows redirecting the data and results stored in the databases to other free development platforms for interactive visualization, as shown below with indicative BIM models (to be closed in a later phase of MULTICLIMACT).

Fig. 9. Interactive DT for pre-designed pavement and NBS solutions showing perspective and section views with real time digital data panels.

Fig. 10. Interactive DT showing access to the dashboard of the temperature measured by the embedded fiber optic sensors (transmitted in real-time from the laboratory tests shown before).

Along with internal pavement and bioswale sensing, it is proposed to install street poles (as shown in the two preceding images) with IoT sensors to monitor and evaluate the impact on reducing the heat-island effect (doing the same also in nearby contrast locations in BCN without these new MULTICLIMACT materials and technologies to improve urban resilience). Accurate representations will be generated for the system when deployed in the future BCN pilot scenario, generating a common data environment in which geometric and sensor data (real time and historical) will be accessible and linked together to achieve functionalities assimilable to an interactive Digital Twin of the urban scale solutions, being also possible the automatic redirection of the processed data and metrics to other platforms with a broader approach within the project.

V. CONCLUSIONS

- A robust solution is designed and assembled for real-time monitoring in urban environments, being fully functional with a customized selection of different types of sensors in terms of technology, measured magnitudes and communications. The solution is scalable and easily adaptable to new sensors.
- First designs of the solutions to mitigate the heat-island effect, namely the new asphalt concrete pavement with recycled glass and clear aggregates and the bioretention swale, have been addressed and their monitoring variables have been determined to evaluate their performance.
- Sensors have been selected to measure the temperature and humidity outside the urban pavement, bioswale and nearby areas (In-house MEMS IoT devices), measure the temperature and strain inside the pavement (custom-made FBG array by HBK) and detect the changes in the water level inside the bioretention swale (new generation of commercial Sigfox stand-alone ultrasonic distance meters) to assess the infiltration rate. All of them measure satisfactorily in comparable cases, or in other urban

outdoor cases, and successfully report their data to the monitoring platform by integrating them into contextual BIM visualizations, being also the architecture adaptable in this step to different development platforms for 3D contextualization.

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